

Abstract**LEXICAL-SEMANTIC BRANCHING OF THE CONCEPT
«YOUTH» IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES****Abduazizova Munisa Muzaffar qizi**Doctoral student of the Tashkent state university of
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The purpose of this study is to reveal the linguistic significance of the concept theory by means of analyzes and to consider the concept of “youth” in two typological groups and within the framework of languages belonging to different language families - Uzbek and English - which are genetically unrelated. The article presents the concept of “youth” in the form of networks based on English and Uzbek dictionaries. The different and common features of the concept of “youth” are analyzed in two languages.

Key words: concept, lexeme, lexical-semantic network, cognitive linguistics, linguistics, category, dichotomy, ethnolinguistics.

Concept theory plays an important role in cognitive psychology, which studies the processes of thinking and understanding. It is a system aimed at understanding how people create knowledge about the world, how they understand information, and how they form categories. Concepts are, simply put, the «building blocks» for our thinking. They consist of mental models that reflect the general characteristics of groups of objects, events or ideas. The main aspects of the concept theory include:

- Types of concepts: Concepts can be different. Some have clear boundaries (eg. pen), others are vague (eg. trust). Concepts can be represented by prototypes (the most typical representative of a category), exemplars (objects that do not have all the properties of a category), and properties (characteristics that define a category).
- Formation of concepts: Concepts are formed based on experience. Children learn and develop concepts through interaction with the world. Comparison, generalization and abstraction play an important role in this process.
- Representation of concepts: Concepts can be represented in the mind in different ways, for example, through words, pictures, symbols. Language is an important tool for understanding and communicating concepts.
- Interdependence of concepts: Concepts are related to each other and there may be a hierarchy between them. For example, the concepts of «animal» include lower-level concepts such as «cat» and «dog» [8].

The set of views of an entire people or a specific person about the surrounding realities forms a national conceptual consciousness. The lexical fund of the language plays an important role in the formation of such a conceptual landscape. As a part of the language system, the lexicon functions as a «repository of cultural traditions» that most clearly reflects the worldviews and observations of reality of the representatives of a certain language community. Linguistic and cultural differences are clearly visible in the perception of reality by speakers of different languages. This also creates differences in concept networks. In particular, the concept of «youth» represents a universal component of human culture. When

analyzing these conceptual groups in Uzbek and English languages, we encounter national-cultural differences. In this article, linguistic and cultural differences between the two languages are revealed based on the concept of «youth».

Culture reflects the psychology and philosophy of a people, its mentality, history, ideas about the world, and its own belief system. In addition, the processes of globalization, the growth of migration processes and the formation of linguistic consciousness cannot fail to influence the ethnolinguistic and linguistic landscape of the world. At the same time, researchers emphasize the interaction of the linguistic and cultural landscape of the world, which has its own characteristics depending on the language and people. This creates certain difficulties when considering the specific features of a particular language system. The dichotomy of «youth» is widespread in the culture of both countries and is a rich material for comparative analysis of similarities and differences in the outlook of two nations - Uzbek and English.

Let's look at the linguistic units expressing the concept of «youth» in English and Uzbek.

According to the «Oxford» explanatory dictionary: «Youth - the period between childhood and adult age; the qualities of vigor, freshness, or immaturity as associated with being young; an early stage in the development of something; young people considered as a group» [5].

In the «Collins» dictionary, the lexeme «youth» is defined as follows: «the quality or condition of being young, immature, or inexperienced; the period between childhood and maturity, esp. adolescence and early adulthood; the freshness, vigor, or vitality characteristic of young people; any period of early development; young people collectively» [1].

Douglas Harper's «Etymological Dictionary of the English Language» provides the following information about the etymology of the lexeme «youth»: «youth (n.) In Old English «geoguð» «youth; young people, small warriors», geong is related to «young», the etymological root of the word is the abstract noun «yeu» - «vital force, strength» from the ancient proto-Germanic language, with «-itho» suffix is added» [4].

In the «Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language» we come across the following explanation: «1. Being young; the time of youth, period; 2. Adolescence, youth; 3. Behavior, characteristic of young people» [3]. There are no final conclusions about the etymology of this word. According to assumptions, the words «yashil» and «yoshlik» are etymologically cognates, and «yash» (yosh) was used in the meanings of new, fresh.

Based on the interpretation of the «Oxford» explanatory dictionary, it can be seen that the concept of «youth» is derived from the following semantic circles: «period of life», «quality of life», «young people as a group», «early stage of development». [6]. The conceptual framework «Period of life» can be connected with the following associative networks: «childhood» and «adolescence». During these two periods, a person's personality, mental, spiritual and physical abilities are formed. Within the «Childhood» network, it can be divided into sub-sections: «physical development» and «development of cognitive skills».

- «Physical development». In the initial stages, the child learns to crawl, walk, run, talk, etc., this concept network also creates an association with «physical development»: to crawl, to walk, to talk, to run.

- The next link is «development of cognitive skills». At the initial stage of childhood (about 3 years old), the child learns about the world through touch, smells, tastes, and feelings. So, this process can be expressed with the following verbs: to touch, to smell, to taste,

to feel. When a child grows up, he begins to learn about the world through books, asking questions, listening, etc. (to read, to write, to think, to ask, to keep in mind).

- «Emotional development». This subplot includes the following branches: to cry, to smile, to shout, to frown, to laugh.
- «Spiritual development». The child is explained what is bad and what is good, what is right and what is wrong, what can be done and what cannot be done.
- «Adolescence» slot can be represented by the following subsections: «further physical development», «development of cognitive skills», «emotional development», «spiritual development».

Now let's take a closer look at these subslots.

- «Further physical development». At this stage of life, higher physical abilities of a person are formed: strength, energy.
- «Development of cognitive skills». At the «youth» stage, a teenager learns about the world by reading, asking questions, and observing. The most appropriate verbs to describe this conceptual network are: to read, to listen, to reflect, to realize, to ask, to keep in mind, to argue.
- The «emotional development» network of the adolescent period subframe is similar to the «emotional development» subplot of the childhood period subframe, the only difference is the focus on emotional diversity at this stage: to cry, to smile, to shout, to frown, to laugh.
- «Spiritual development». At this stage of life, the spiritual development of a teenager is influenced by books, music, television, the press and the Internet. But the most important influence on the formation of a person is shown by family and society. Accordingly, this part of our concept network can be expressed by the following words: family, society, friends, books, music, TV, Internet.

Thus, we divided the «youth» concept into slots according to age and created subslots according to the skills and qualities that a person acquires at each stage.

Let's look at the structure of the concept of «youth» in the Uzbek language. As we mentioned above, in explanatory dictionaries, the word «youth» has only one meaning – the period of infancy and maturity. However, we suggest dividing the concept of «youth» into subframes, similar to the English concept of «youth». Thus, we described 4 small conceptual branches in the Uzbek language: «life period», «vital qualities», «youth as a group», «early stage of development». The Lifetime subframe is divided into slots such as childhood and adolescence. The «Childhood» network, in turn, can be divided into such subsections as «physical development», «perception», «emotional development», «spiritual development». The initial stages are characterized by the child's learning to crawl, walk, run, talk, etc. The following are the main associations in the Uzbek language of this period: crawling, walking, running, talking. A child's acquaintance with the outside world occurs through emotional perception. This means knowing through different touch, smells, tastes. As the child grows and develops, he learns to read, listens when people speak to him, and asks questions. This stage includes the following series of verbs: read, listen, ask questions. In the East, the spiritual development of a child is connected with network concepts such as family environment, education, neighborhood and friends, and reading, and this link is not found in the conceptual network of «youth» in the English language.

Analyzing the concept of «youth» in English and Uzbek languages, we came to the following conclusions: 1. The concept of «youth» presented in the form of a network in both languages can be divided into 4 small conceptual frameworks: «life period»; «quality of life»; «youth as a group» or «youth as people in a collective sense»; «early stage of development»; 2. The basis of the lexical-semantic group «youth» in English is the lexeme «youth», and in the Uzbek language it is the lexeme «yoshlik»; 3) a comparative analysis of the meanings of the word «youth» and the English word «youth» showed that the English concept «youth» has a wider conceptual network.

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